

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KALALA****FIRST NAME: SAPARD****PROGRAM CODE: LLM****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied uses US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Academic & Essay writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Avoiding plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-6)
3. In-Text Citation (EUCLID 2019, 6)
4. Quotations (EUCLID 2019, 6-8)
5. Paraphrasing (EUCLID 2019, 8-10)
6. Citations (EUCLID 2019, 10-13)
7. American vs. British English (2019, 27-35)

ROAD TO SUCCESS IN ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

As students, we are always required to write reports and essays for coursework as well as final examinations. However, one of the most formidable challenges we encounter is writing good academic essays that are free from errors and inconsistencies. In academic writing, reference, quotation, in-text citation, capitalizations, abbreviations, paraphrasing, introduction, summary, and conclusion are used to present those assignments and reports, thus clearly articulating or rather communicating individual's thoughts to enhance their understandability not only to the marker but also other interested readers (Bailey 2014, 6). Fundamentally, the process of writing incorporates ideas and research generated by other people. In academic writing, most of these elements help in acknowledging the sources consulted in the process of research work besides ensuring the work is presented neatly and in the best way possible.

2) PURPOSE OF RESEARCH

First, as a way crediting the author from whom ideas and words are borrowed from references, quoting, in-text citation and paraphrasing are necessary and plays an undeniable role in demonstrating respect for the intellectual property rights of the other scholars as well as acknowledging them for their contribution in that particular field of study (EUCLID 2019,

5). More specifically, referencing and quoting provide proof of having consulted various works thus supporting claims and assertions made in reports assignments as well as reports. In order to navigate through a particular academic project, research is necessary to ensure accurate references are provided to the readers besides facilitates tracing of the used information sources (Horkoff 2015, 23). Also, research is necessary for avoiding possibilities of plagiarism and ensures the highest academic integrity is upheld. In the academic community, authors are bound to maintain the integrity by appropriately using and citing the work of the people rightfully. The purpose of paraphrasing is to information and ideas of other authors regarding a particular topic in the current writer's own wording (EUCLID 2019, 8). Through paraphrasing, learners demonstrate that they sufficiently understood the source to put it in their own wording. Paraphrasing and quoting are used along with in-text citation which provides identification of specific source consulted thus facilitating the easy location of the source in the bibliography by the readers.

Other critical elements of international academic writing include capitalization, abbreviation, introduction, summary, and conclusion. Capitalization, just punctuation facilitates the conveyance of critical information. Their purpose in research is to indicate the commencement of a new sentence besides signifying the uniqueness of proper nouns that include names of things, places, and particular person. Abbreviations are used to enhance convenience by using initial parts of a phrase or name. In the research they facilitate shorter and simple titles, for instance, Information and Communications Technology can be abbreviated as ICT. Introduction in research work creates establishes credibility and creates a first impression (Mayer 2012, 171). It grabs the attention of the audience and explains the outline or rather the purpose of the entire paper. A summary usually provides an outline that highlights the major points of findings or analysis which makes readers of your work. The conclusion provides readers with a synthesis of the information provided within the entire essay. The author gives their opinions with respect to the topic in question; it also transitions the reader to the real-life situation thus facilitating reflection of the world's realities.

In order to avoid violating academic integrity, research on the above elements is necessary and helps writers in learning essential writing and research skills. It is necessary to provide readers with comprehensive references and in-text citations to enable them to find more details in connection with the source if they wish to look into the topic in detail. Furthermore, introduction, summary, conclusion, capitalization, and quotes in academic writing help in bringing clarity into the insights of the author and helps the reader understand the ideas expressed by various sources.

3) REFERENCING AND QUOTATION SYSTEMS

“Referencing guards against plagiarism, a serious academic offence” (EUCLID 2019, 4). Various academic disciplines employ various methods of referencing since they impeccably work with various types of text used commonly in those particular disciplines. For instance, the Modern Language Association is most preferable in theatre, English Literature, and Film.

a) Methods of Referencing

In Turabian style, citations can be listed in the footnotes or the body of the text. The two methods commonly used in Turabian include the author-date and notes and bibliography. Those working in disciplines such as arts, history, and literature prefer the notes and bibliography method while those working in sciences prefer the author-date system (Williams & Davis 2017, 74). Sequential endnotes or rather footnotes are used in notes and bibliography methods whereby the notes are presented as superscripts in the text in which citation is intended and a separate bibliography is also maintained at the end of the document. The in-text citations include the surname of the authors, year of publication, and the specific page which consulted.

b) Systems of Quotation

Quoting is mean through which authors directly express the words of someone else and alludes them at the beginning of the end of the quote (EUCLID 2019, 6). The writer prefers the exact wording of the source to substantiate their argument and define or clarify details being deliberated. There are two common methods of the quotation: short quotations and block or long quotations. The short quotation may be as little as one word and goes to a maximum of three sentences. Ideally, these methods of quoting do not go past forty words (Bailey 2014, 62). Often, writers employ the use of attributive tags thus fluidly incorporating the essential quote. The other commonly used method of quoting is the block quotation and it involves more than forty words quoted. Block quotations are employed when critical but long information cannot be successfully paraphrased or when the author wants the original writer to think for you in the entire work.

i) *In-Text Citation*

The in-text citation is a mode of referencing where the authors of academic essays make allusions within the body of their work. In most methods of referencing, in-text citations provide the author of the work and year of publication. Also, some methods provide author and specific page consulted (Pears and Shields 2019, 52). Usually, they are included when a source is quoted, paraphrased, summarized, or even referred to. Commonly, in Turabian citation, author and date method are used especially in social, physical, and natural sciences.

ii) *Capitalization and Abbreviation*

Capitalization involves the use of the upper case to emphasize major headings and proper nouns. It is used to portray the change in meanings, beginning of new sentences, and nouns. They are part of punctuations and helps in better interpretation and understanding of sentences by readers (EUCLID 2019, 45). Abbreviating, on the other hand, refers to the use of initials or acronyms within the text. While they are never encouraged, they are used whenever there is no better way of presenting the phrase of multiple words. They should be used whenever readers are cognizant of their meanings. They are introduced after mentioning the initial phrase within the text. For instance, the Master of Business Administration.

4) INTRODUCTION AND PARAPHRASING

Most of the essays begin with researching the topic and writing main ideas regarding the topic of research constituting an introduction. Defining the question and analyzing the task are the pillars to success of any academic writing (EUCLID 2019, 1). The introduction is aimed at capturing the readers' attention and provides them with a yearning to explore further what is contained within the entire text. It highlights the outline of the paper pointing out the main arguments or rather the thesis of the essay. To avoid one of the serious offenses in writing, expressing someone else ideas differently is a fundamental element of international academic writing, this is termed as paraphrasing (EUCLID 2019, 8). It reduces unnecessary quoting within the essay by rearranging the structure of sentences as well as changing multiple words to deviate from what the initial author had written thus avoiding plagiarism.

5) CONCLUSION

In nonfiction writing, it is necessary to incorporate a summary of findings in the conclusion. Summary recapitulates critical points of the essay or report thus reinforcing its content. Literary, summary ties things up thus eliminating the possibility of confusion among readers of the essay. It demonstrates the significance of the ideas included in the essay (Tshotsho 2015, 9). On the other hand, in conclusion, the author defends their argument and may reflect on world reality. The conclusion closes the paper and provides the author's opinion regarding the topic.

In recap and in my opinion, it is undeniably evident that referencing, quoting, in-text citations, capitalization, abbreviating, paraphrasing, introduction, summary, and conclusion play a very vital role in academic writing. They help in giving attribution to authors for their contribution in particulars wording or ideas besides ensuring a systematic and clear essay is presented. Fundamentally, the aforementioned elements help in upholding the utmost academic integrity that helps the writer to avoid the tragic consequences of plagiarism and plays a central role in the creation of presentable and well-structured essays. They stimulate thinking among the learners thus being an ability to write in their own words and come up with original work out of already existing sources. They finally help in advancing the creativity and writing skills of learners in the dynamic learning and working environment.

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